

DESIGN OF MULTILAYER COMPOSITE-ANTENNA-STRUCTURE CONSIDERING ADHESIVE EFFECTS

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SUMMARY: Our objective in this work was to design a Composite-Antenna-Structure (CAS) for satellite communication and investigate the antenna performances considering adhesive effects. “Structural surface becomes an antenna.” This term, CAS, indicates antenna embedding in structural surfaces. The CAS is composed of several composite laminates and Nomex honeycombs, and microstrip antenna elements are inserted between layers with designed configurations. Constituent materials are selected considering electrical contributions as well as mechanical performances. Antenna design with adhesive films are impossible because of their thin and rough distributions between honeycomb and substrate. Therefore, adhesive effects on antenna performances in CAS are experimentally investigated, CAS with targeted radiation characteristics are designed considering adhesive effects.

KEYWORDS: CAS, Composite Antenna Structure, Sandwich Structure, Microstrip Antenna

INTRODUCTION

Communication areas will in the future be expanded by the use of satellite communication and satellite Internet availability in vehicles. To implement these satellite services, especially in vehicles, antenna technology will be central. Antennas located on the surface of a structure take up much space, and suffer from large path-loss and junction-loss. In view of these problems, the Structures Division of the US Air Force’s Wright Laboratory is sponsoring the development and demonstration of CLAS [1]. This program is called “Smart-Skin Structure Technology Demonstration (S3TD)” [2]. The program opted for a multi-arm spiral antenna embedded in a CLAS fuselage panel. The final demonstration article was a structurally effective 36 x 36 inch curved multifunction antenna component panel. It successfully withstood running loads of 4,000 pounds per inch and principal strain levels of 4,700 micro-strain, and featured a broadband (150 MHz to 2.0 GHz), multifunction communication, navigation and identification, and electric warfare (CNI/EW) antenna. The present study aims to design, fabricate and investigate the structural and electrical performances of microstrip antennas of composite sandwich construction as part of the next generation of structural surface technology. This is termed a Composite-Antenna-Structure (CAS). The CAS is composed of several composite laminates and Nomex honeycombs, and microstrip antenna elements are inserted between layers with designed configurations [3-5]. Antenna design with adhesive films are impossible because of their thin and rough distributions between honeycomb and substrate. Therefore, adhesive effects on antenna performances in CAS are experimentally investigated, CAS with targeted impedance and radiation characteristics are designed considering adhesive effects.

BASIC CONCEPT OF THE CAS

A microstrip antenna has significant advantages over conventional antennas in size, ease of fabrication and compatibility with printed circuits, but also defects such as narrow bandwidth and low efficiency. To overcome these problems a new concept, the strip-slot-foam-inverted patch (SSFIP) antenna, has been developed [6,7]. To radiate efficiently, an antenna should be built on a thick substrate of low-permittivity material to prevent large electromagnetic fields concentrating within the substrate. A multilayer structure was therefore developed to combine the advantages of foam materials with non-resonant slot coupling and broadbanding techniques. This widens the frequency bandwidth about tenfold with respect to standard microstrip antennas. It is called a Strip-Slot-Foam-Inverted Patch antenna (SSFIP) and is shown in Fig. 1, which indicates the sequence of features seen by the signal as it emerges from the feed line and propagates into the free space above the patch. This CAS is an integrated composite of sandwich structure and SSFIP multi-layer microstrip antenna. CAS consists of two composite laminates (substrates), two honeycomb cores, three conducting materials (patch, slot, feedline), and a shielding plane. Composite laminates of low electrical loss and Nomex honeycomb cores of low-permittivity prevent surface wave propagation and increase the bandwidth. The radiating patches are deposited on the underside of a substrate that serves as a protective cover. Electrical signals are fed, via wide coupling slots, by a microstrip line located on a high-quality dielectric substrate beneath the ground plane.

Fig. 1: Concept of CAS

The face sheet properties required to sustain the structural load must not impair antenna performance. Face sheets must therefore have a low dielectric constant and must carry a significant portion of the in-plane load. The top sheet must be quite thin so that its effect on antenna characteristics is small, but its thickness must provide the necessary structural rigidity.

The honeycomb cores transmit between the face sheets the shear induced by bending loads, and provide the air gap required by the antenna. The radiating patch is placed on an upper honeycomb core. Patch on thick honeycomb core has wider resonance, leading to larger bandwidths. However, as the thickness of the upper honeycomb core increases, coupling from

the slot to the patch is reduced. The thickness of the bottom honeycomb core is determined by requirements of structural rigidity.

DESIGN PROCEDURE

We designed single patch antenna. The antenna has center frequency of 7 GHz resonant. This has a square patch and characteristic impedance of 50Ω . Fig. 2 shows a single element of the stack. The patch size for center frequency of 7 GHz resonant is 13 mm.

Fig.2: Exploded view of CAS structure

In selecting CAS materials, electrical performance and mechanical efficiency must be considered. The substrate was a woven glass fiber-reinforced plastic. This has superior electrical and mechanical properties and is a low loss material, allowing the fabrication of a high frequency circuit. Nomex honeycomb was used as a core material, since it is lightweight and strong. It has a low dielectric constant that makes it suitable for microwave applications. Nomex honeycomb of thickness 2.54 mm was used for the upper core to achieve both wide bandwidth and good coupling between slot and patch. Between the feedline and the shielding plane, a honeycomb core of thickness 2.54 mm. For the shielding plane, a woven glass fiber-reinforced plastic of thickness 1 mm was used to provide structural support as well as reducing back radiation. Table 1 gives the properties of constituent materials.

Table 1: Properties of constituent materials

(ϵ_r : dielectric constant, $\tan \delta$: loss tangent, E: tensile modulus, G: shear modulus, σ_u : tensile strength)

Layer	Material	Electrical	Mechanical
Outer facesheet	Woven GFRP (Rogers)	$\epsilon_r = 3.48$ $\tan \delta = 0.004$	$E = 15.5$ [GPa] $\sigma_u = 123$ [MPa]
Honeycomb	Nomex Honeycomb (Hexcel Composite)	$\epsilon_r = 1.1$ $\tan \delta \approx$ nearly zero	$G = 88.63$ [MPa] In ribbon direction
Dielectric	Woven GFRP (Rogers)	$\epsilon_r = 3.38$ $\tan \delta = 0.0027$	$E = 16.5$ [GPa] $\sigma_u = 96.5$ [MPa]
Supporter	Woven GFRP (SK Chemical)	structural use	$E = 25.4$ [GPa] $\sigma_u = 573.6$ [MPa]

The adhesive used to bond the different layers and prevent air gaps has an effect on antenna performance.

ANTENNA PERFORMANCES COMPARISON

First, we measured the antenna performances before insert the adhesive between the each materials of the CAS. Secondly, the assembly was then cured under pressure in an autoclave using the recommended curing cycle for this adhesive (125 °C for 90 minutes under pressure of 3 kgf/cm²). Thirdly, we measured again the performances of the antenna. Fig. 3 shows the reflection coefficient. There are slight decrease of the center frequency and the reflection coefficient. There is an decrease of 0.45 GHz of center frequency. Radiation patterns in the relevant frequency range are shown in Fig. 4. The radiation patterns are same over the bandwidth, but the gain at 7 GHz decreases from 7.25 dBi to 6.80 dBi. This is a consequence of using the adhesive film.

Fig.3: Impedance characteristics compassion of 7 GHz single CAS

Fig. 4: Radiation patterns of 7 GHz single CAS (measured at 7 GHz)

DESIGN OF CAS CONSIDERING OF ADHESIVE EFFECTS AND EXPERIMENT

Based on adhesive effects, we designed again a single patch antenna. The antenna was fabricated center frequency of 7.4 GHz resonant for center frequency of 7GHz resonant. So, patch size was reduced in 13mm to 12.04 mm. Next, the assembly was then cured, and we measure the antenna performances. The results are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. The antenna which was designed considering of adhesive effect resonated at the same frequency non using adhesive, and the gain at 7 GHz is 6.65 dBi. The result of the experiment was that we could get the performance to want after we used the adhesive.

Fig.5: Impedance characteristics comparison of 7 GHz single CAS (after curing, designed at 7GHz considering adhesive effects)

Fig.6: Radiation patterns of 7 GHz single CAS (after curing, designed at 7 GHz considering adhesive effects, measured at 7 GHz)

CONCLUSION

We have designed, fabricated and experimented a Composite-Antenna-Structure (CAS). The antenna elements inserted were designed to sandwich structure. The adhesive used to bond the different layers and prevent air gaps has an effect on antenna performance. In particular, the center frequency decreases by a few percent, dielectric losses increase slightly

These effects are particularly marked for epoxy adhesive, which is used because mechanical rigidity is important. By the use of experimental correction factors during the design process, the effect of the adhesive can be compensated.

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